

The Effect of Work Stress and Work Values on Turnover Intention of Generation Z Employees in Call Center Company (Case Study of PT ABC in Java, Indonesia)

Darian Kashfitanto¹, Hary Febriansyah²

^{1,2} School of Business and Management, Bandung Institute of Technology, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: A various of previous research have found that different generation has a positive and negative traits. Generation Z is a generation that born between 1995 and 2012. Generation Z have distinct qualities including the need for convenience, are watchful and worried about their emotional, physical, and financial safety, and also have a realistic view of the importance of their profession. There has been found a high turnover rate of the Generation Z. Employees in a call center interact with customers over the phone or through other technological devices. Because of the constant interaction with angry customers seeking information, support, and help, working at a call center can be difficult. This exposes the customer service representative to a range of stressful circumstances and negative feelings. The employees experience work related stress and are emotionally exhausted, and tend to express themselves by increasing their intention to leave the company. The main issues in many call centers include a high employee turnover rate, which is believed to be as high as 40% annually also it is believed that many contact centers face is a high employee turnover rate that is higher than any other industries.

PT ABC is a focused company specializes in outsourcing business process management with a call center business which is part of BPO or Business Process Outsourcing. The business emphasis is one of the PT ABC has held for a very long time. Based on the interview with HR Support of the PT ABC in Bandung, the TAM division is the division that consider with the most and the highest employee turnover rate compared to other divisions and the majority are the young employees, every month turnover is found in the division, one of the reason stated by the HR Officer is that the factor of the turnover probably due to the workload. This research was made using a quantitative method and random sampling that have been conducted in April 2023 in PT ABC in Java, Indonesia. Based on the previous research this research assumes that work stress and work values affecting turnover intention of the Generation Z, this research conducted to prove that the assumption above is right. Data collected in this research was using interview and the measurement scales used are work stress and turnover intention scale adapted by Agustina (2022) and work values scale by Sulistiobudi & Hutabarat (2022), which have been tested using validity and reliability. This research is analyzed using multiple linear regression using SPSS 25 to determine the effect of the variables. Based on the results of the data processing, there is social dimension of work value, leadership attitude and organizational structure of work stress dimensions that impacted to Generation Z employees in PT ABC. This research contributes to understand the Generation Z characteristic in the work environment. It also contributes and helps how company handle the employees especially the Generation Z. Author recommends that next researcher that using other variables in the company to broaden and deepen the researchs of Generation z in the call center.

KEYWORDS: Call Center, Employee Turnover, Generation Z, Management, Turnover Intention.

INTRODUCTION

Based on Indonesia's population census data in 2018, 67.6 % of the Indonesian population is in production age, which is between 15 – 64 years old, while Indonesian population census in 2020 found that 27.94% of the total population or 74.93 million people in Indonesia is Gen Z (Jayani, 2021). Generation Z is an individual that born between 1995 and 2012 (Francis & Hoefel, 2018). Previous research revealed that each different generation has positive and negative traits that affect job outcomes (Yu, et al., 2022). Wingard (2021) found that a high percentage of Generation Z are intent to switch and quit the job. A research findings by Deloitte (2019), found that the reported turnover rate in Indonesia was increased to more than 10% after Generation Z entered the workforce.

A call center is a type of workplace where employees connect with consumers via the phone or through other computer based technologies (Doellgast & O'Brady, 2020). The activities is focused on receiving calls from consumers who contact the call center

to complain and encounter problems, other activity is they also involved in selling and telemarketing (Zito, et al., 2018). The job is considered to be one of the most stressful work environment and jobs in the world economy (Posey, 2019; Doellgast & O'Brady, 2020), it is also considered as a workforce where a frequent organizations experience a high employee turnover than in other jobs (Dhanpat, 2018) As a consequence of the frequent interaction with clients, the need for communication skills and the repetitive nature of the work, employees performance is frequently monitored, which reduces their autonomy and puts pressure on the daily job (Zito, et al., 2018). Working at a call center can be challenging because of the constant contact with clients who frequently exhibit anger while asking for information, support and assistance. This exposes the customer care professional to a variety of stressful situations and bad emotions (Zito, et al., 2018). The extensive use of computerized monitoring strict scheduling and break regulations, and high performance expectations are the traits of call centers (Zito, et al., 2018). As result a high employee turnover, with an estimated annually turnover rate as high as 40% is the main problems in many call centers (Posey, 2019).

High employee turnover is one of the main issues facing many contact centers. These workers are emotionally spent and suffering from role stress. In this situation, they are probably displaying resigning intentions, which allude to a desire to leave the company (Posey, 2019).

BUSINESS ISSUE

PT ABC is a focused company specializes in outsourcing business process management with a call center business which is part of BPO or Business Process Outsourcing. The business emphasis is one of the PT ABC has held for a very long time.

Based on the interview with HR Support of the PT ABC in Bandung, the TAM division is the division that consider with the most and the highest employee turnover rate compared to other divisions and the majority are the young employees, every month turnover is found in the division, one of the reason stated by the HR Officer is that the factor of the turnover probably due to the workload.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work Stress

Work stress is defined as a negative reaction that individuals have to undue expectations and demands placed on them at work. People may experience work stress as a reaction when their knowledge and abilities are not matched by the demands and pressures of their jobs (Sharma, Ms. Sharma, & Agarwal, June 2021). Based on the theory of Handoko (2004) there are four indicators of work stress, those are:

A. Task Demand

An element connected to one's job, such as workplace policies and practices (Nanda, 2019)

B. Role Demand

Associated with the pressure placed on a person as a result of the specific role they have in an organization (Nanda, 2019).

C. Organizational Structure

It can be stressful for employees if the organization's form and structure are ambiguous and persists for a long time. Individuals' positions within an organizational structure can also show how stress levels are experienced (Nanda, 2019).

D. Leadership Attitude

The leadership style towards their staff members can be a source of stress for them; if a manager does not pay close attention to his staff, he will feel down and careless (Nanda, 2019).

Work stress can be caused by many factors, there are several factors of work stress that affects generation Z the most, based on the research of (Stobiecka & Kania, 2022) those are:

A. Work Overload

The amount of work a person must complete is referred to as their workload. Workload can also be categorized as quantitative or qualitative, depending on how much work needs to be done overall and how tough the tasks are (Arshad, Shahidan, Siam, & Alshuaibi, 2020). It is one of many cause of work stress to Generation Z (Stobiecka & Kania, 2022).

B. Employee Relations

The relations between employees in the workplace environment is one other factors that causing work stress for Generation Z (Stobiecka & Kania, 2022).

C. Leaders

Generation Z finds stress in the leader's behavior, such as when they treat workers poorly.

Work Values

People's behaviors are significantly influenced by their values, which have an impact on their perceptions, attitudes, and motives. People's values influence how broadly they view what is acceptable or undesirable, but they also have values that are particular to certain occasions or circumstances, such as their values at work. The definition of work values is described as a person's overall work goals and the characteristics of a job that are crucial to that person's job satisfaction (Kr & Rajendran, 2019). based on the theory of Twenge et al. (2010) to capture the different values of different generation's perspective (Sulistiobudi & Hutabarat, 2022), those dimensions are:

A. Leisure

Leisure is defined as having access to free time, vacation, and independence from responsibility. A person who values their leisure time works to land a career that will allow them more time for other activities (Kr & Rajendran, 2019). When individuals are more excited in occupations that can fit their family and personal lives, leisure is also valued (Sulistiobudi & Hutabarat, 2022). A stronger career will emerge from fulfilling those needs.

B. Extrinsic

Values that are extrinsically oriented people hold include things like power, an emphasis on status, hierarchical roles, and reward (Kr & Rajendran, 2019). Employees in the current generation may place a greater emphasis on employment that offer extrinsic incentives as a result of current economic trends (Sulistiobudi & Hutabarat, 2022). Higher salaries have been demonstrated to increase workplace satisfaction for extrinsically motivated workers (Kr & Rajendran, 2019). Extrinsic reward will result in good performance and happiness for employees (Sulistiobudi & Hutabarat, 2022).

C. Intrinsic

It describes as employees reflecting intrinsic work values as having a natural desire to grow and develop. Intrinsic values is also associated with an increased well-being since their ambition to satisfy psychological needs, such as competence and autonomy (Kr & Rajendran, 2019) also includes work that is tough, improving abilities, allowing employees to grow, offering variety and responsibility, offering challenges, allowing employees to appreciate their results, and having a big impact on others are all intrinsic benefits (Sulistiobudi & Hutabarat, 2022).

D. Altruistic

Altruistic rewards include the drive to involves the ambition to helping others while contributing to the society. (Kr & Rajendran, 2019)Altruism is the disposition to assist someone without taking into account one's own benefits (Sulistiobudi & Hutabarat, 2022).

E. Social Rewards

The need to relate to and associate with groups of people in a variety of jobs is a social pleasure. Social networking platforms today can give the idea that there is a greater need for social interaction and the tracking of interpersonal interactions (Sulistiobudi & Hutabarat, 2022).

Turnover Intention

Based on Mobley (2011) Turnover Intention is a cause derives from employees intention to freely quit their jobs and move to other jobs in accordance to their own desire (Mobley W. H., 2011). Based on Agustina, (2022) explained that there are three Indicators of turnover intention, those are:

A. Thinking and Intention of Quitting

The emergence of dissatisfaction felt by the employees that causing the employees to think to leave the job

B. Intention to Find a New Job

The desires of the employees to find a new job

Several factors were found affecting turnover intention in many previous researches, some of them are:

A. Work Stress

Definition used in this study is work stress is defined as a negative reaction that individuals have to undue expectations and demands placed on them at work. People may experience work stress as a reaction when their knowledge and abilities

are not matched by the demands and pressures of their jobs (Sharma, Ms. Sharma, & Agarwal, June 2021). A previous study found that work stress in Generation Z affect their intention to leave their job (Maulana, 2022)

B. Organizational Commitment

Defines organizational commitment as a personal force that opposes one's participation in a specific organization, which is typically characterized by at least three factors: (1) a strong commitment to upholding the organization's goals and principles; (2) a strong willingness to put forth all possible effort on its behalf; and (3) a strong desire to keep one's membership in the organization (Santoso, Sitompul, & Budiarmanto, 2018). A study conducted by Budiman & Tan (2022) found that organizational commitment have an effect on turnover intention for Generation Z employees.

C. Work Values

The definition used in this study is work values described as a person's overall work goals and the characteristics of a job that are crucial to that person's job satisfaction (Kr & Rajendran, 2019). A study of Hanaty (2022) found that there is a significant effect of workplace values on turnover intention of Generation Z.

D. Employee Engagement

Employee engagement is demonstrated in the way that they behave emotionally, cognitively, and physically. Employee commitment to their performance role and dedication to the job at hand. The cognitive component of employee engagement is concerned with how employees perceive organizational elements such how they should be led, who should lead them, and the conditions under which they must work (Saks, 2006; Filatrovi & Attiq, 2020). A study conducted by Dhoundiyal, Soni, & Kumari (2022) found that employee engagement have a significant effect on turnover intention amongst Generation Z employees in Mumbai.

E. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is characterized as a sense of personal accomplishment and success. Most people agree that it has a significant effect on both personal and professional well-being as well as productivity and performance at work. Worker satisfaction is defined as enjoying one's work, performing it effectively, and receiving recognition for one's efforts (Dziuba, Ingaldi, & Zhuravskaya, 2020). A study conducted by Dhoundiyal, Soni, & Kumari (2022) found that job satisfaction have a significant effect on turnover intention amongst Generation Z employees in Mumbai.

Generation Z

Generation Z, or those born between 1995 and 2010, are real digital natives who have grown up with the internet, social media, and mobile technology (Francis & Hoefel, 2018). There are different behaviors and values in each generation (Gaan & Shin, 2022). Gen Z members place a higher emphasis on soft skills than on hard abilities when considering the factors that they see as crucial for the advancement of their professional lives. This trait is driven by Generation Z's need for a flexible work schedule, which we identify with the dynamic and globalized environment in which this generation was raised and now lives (Racolta-Paina & Irini, 2021). Due to the quickening pace of changes, Gen Z's behavior shows a lack of organizational identity and suggests that the generation does not prioritize long devotion to companies (Gaan & Shin, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

This research was made using a quantitative method and a purposive, non probability sampling that had been conducted in April 2023 in PT ABC in Java. The sample are Generation Z who are working in call center in PT ABC. Based on Bryman (2012) quantitative is a research method that prioritizing quantitative numerical in collecting and analyzing data (Xueting, 2022). The questionnaire used in this research are work values questionnaire adapted by Sulistiobudi & Hutabarat (2022), work stress and turnover intention questionnaire are using questionnaire adapted by Agustina (2022)

Figure 1. 1 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual above describes of this research, based on the conceptual framework above, the hypothesis for this research are:

H1 : Work value affects turnover intention of Generation Z employee in PT ABC

H2 : Work stress affects turnover intention of Generation Z employee in PT ABC

H3 : Work value and work stress affect turnover intention of Generation Z employee in PT ABC

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of the Respondent

Table 1. Characteristics of The Respondent 1

Gender	Frequencies	Percentage
Male	102	35.2%
Female	188	64.8%
Total	290	100%
Age	Frequencies	Percentage
17-20 years	7	2.41%
21-25 years	152	52.41%
26-28 years	131	45.17%
Total	290	100%

Table 2. Characteristics of The Respondent 2

Educations	Frequencies	Percentage
High School	70	24.1%
Diploma degree	36	12.4%
Bachelor degree	182	62.8%
Master degree	2	0.7%
Total	290	100%

Table 3. Characteristics of The Respondent 3

Length of work	Frequencies	Percentage
<1 year	90	31.0%
1-2 years	44	15.2%
>2 years	156	53.8%
Total	290	100%
Work Location	Frequencies	Percentage
Bandung	72	24.8%
Bogor	54	18.6%
Tangsel	45	15.5%
Semarang	71	24.5%
Malang	48	16.6%
Total	290	100%

Multiple Linear Regression

1) T-test

Table 4. T-test

Variable	Coefficient	T - Statistic	Sig
(Constant)	3.240		
Work Value	-0.462	-7.086	0.000
Work Stress	0.546	10.491	0.000

Based on the regression results above, the regression model obtained is as follows :

$$\text{Turnover intention} = 3.240 - 0.462 (X1) + 0.546 (X2)$$

A constant value of 3.240 means that there is a constant increase in turnover intention of 3.240 regardless of the value of work value and work stress. If it is assumed that work value and work stress are 0, then a purchase decision is 3.240 The work value variable has a T – value of -7.086 and a significance of 0.000 so that the significance value is less than 0.05, so that there is a significant partial effect of the work value variable on turnover intention. The regression coefficient value is -0.462 indicating a negative effect, meaning that the higher the work value, the lower the turnover intention and vice versa. The coefficient value indicates that turnover intention will decrease by 0.462 units for every one unit incirease in work value.The work stress variable has a T value of 10.491 and a significance of 0.000. If the significance value is less than 0.05 it indicates that there is a significant partial effect of the work stress variable on turnover intention. The regression coefficient value of 0.546 indicates a positive effect, meaning that the higher the work stress, the higher the turnover intention and vice versa. The coefficient value also means that turnover intention will increase by 0.546 units for every one unit increase in work stress.

2) F-test

Table 5. F-test

Variable	F stat; Sig
Work Value Dan Work Stress → Turnover Intention	F stat = 99,997 ; Sig = 0,000

There is a mutual influence between the independent variables if the calculated F value is greater than the F table and the significance is less than 0.05, The F – count is 99.997 and the significance is less than 0.05. it can be concluded that there is a simultaneous effect of work values and work stress on turnover intention.

3) R square

Table 6. R Square

Variable	R ²
Work Value Dan Work Stress→ Turnover Intention	0.411

R square or the coefficient of determination is a value that indicates how much the independent variable can explain the dependent variable. The coefficient of determination test (R²) aims to see what proportion of the independent variables jointly affect the dependent variable. The coefficient of determination aims to determine the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The result of the coefficient of determination above is 0.411 which means that work value and work stress can affect turnover intention by 41.1% while the remaining 58.9% is influenced by other variables that are not the focus of this study.

Multiple Linear Regression for Each Dimensions of Variables

1) T-test

Table 7. T - Test for Each Dimensions

Variable	Coefficient	T - Statistics	Sig
(Constant)	3.280		
Leisure	-0.068	-0.894	0.372
Intrinsic	-0.165	-1.488	0.138
Altruistic	-0.011	-0.114	0.909
Social	-0.202	-2.248	0.025
Extrinsic	-0.019	-0.233	0.816
Job demand	0.065	0.824	0.411
Role demand	0.133	1.633	0.104
Organization structure	0.202	2.548	0.011
Leadership attitude	0.147	2.643	0.009

Based on the regression results, the regression model is obtained as follows :

$$\text{Turnover intention} = 3.28 - 0.068 (\text{Leisure}) - 0.165 (\text{Intrinsic}) - 0.011 (\text{Altruistic}) - 0.202 (\text{Social}) - 0.019 (\text{Extrinsic}) + 0.065 (\text{Job demand}) + 0.133 (\text{Role demand}) + 0.202 (\text{Organization structure}) + 0.147 (\text{Leadership attitude})$$

A constant value of 3.280 means that there is a constant increase in turnover intention of 3.280 regardless of the value of each dimension. If it is assumed that each dimension has a value of 0, then the turnover intention would be 30.280. in the work value variable there are leisure, intrinsic, altruistic and extrinsic dimensions are not affect turnover intention, while in the work stress variable there are job demand and role demand are not affect turnover intention. There is one dimension in the work value is obtained that influences turnover intention, it is social dimension. The social dimension has a t – count of -2.248 and a significance of 0.025, it has significance value less than 0.05 meaning that there is a partial effect of the social dimension on turnover intention. The regression coefficient value of -0.202 indicates a negative effect, meaning that the higher the social, the lower the turnover intention and vice versa.

There are two dimensions of work stress influence turnover intention. First, it is the organization structure dimension. The organization structure dimension has a t – value of 2.548 and a significance of 0.011 so that the significance value is less than 0.05, meaning it has a significant partial effect of the organization structure dimension on turnover intention. The regression coefficient value of 0.202 indicates a positive influence, meaning that the higher the dimensions of the organization structure, the turnover intention will increase and vice versa. This coefficient value also means that turnover intention will increase by 0.202 units for every one – unit increase in the organization structure dimension.

Second dimension of work stress that influences turnover intention is leadership attitude dimension. It has t – count value of 2.643 and a significance of 0.009 so that the significance value is less than 0.05, meaning that there is a partially significant effect of the leadership attitude on turnover intention. The regression coefficient value of 0.147 indicates a positive influence, meaning that the

higher the leadership attitude dimension, the turnover intention will increase by 0.147 units for every one – unit increase in the leadership attitude dimension.

2) F-test

Table 8. F - Test for Each Dimensions

Variable	F stat; Sig
Leisure, Intrinsic, Altruistic, Social, Extrinsic, Job Demand, Role Demand, Organization Structure, Leadership Attitude → Turnover Intention	F stat=22.671 ; Sig= 0,000

There is an effect between each independent variable if the F – count value is greater than the F -table and the significance is less than 0.05. the F – count is 22.671 and the significance is 0.000 so the significance is less than 0.05 meaning that there is a simultaneous effect of leisure, intrinsic, altruistic, social, extrinsic, job demand, role demand, organization structure and leadership attitude on turnover intention.

3) R Square

Table 9. R Square for Each Dimensions

Variable	R ²
Leisure, Intrinsic, Altruistic, Social, Extrinsic, Job Demand, Role Demand, Organization Structure, Dan Leadership Attitude → Turnover Intention	0.422

The result of the coefficient of determination above is 0.422 which can be said to be leisure, intrinsic, altruistic, social, extrinsic, job demand, role demand can affect turnover intention by 42.2% while the remaining 57.8% is influenced by variables which are not the focus of this research

4) Examination of Hypothesis

1. Work Value affects Turnover Intention of Generation Z Employee in PT ABC in Java

Based on the T – test result of the work value variable it has significance value of 0.000 meaning that if the significance value is less than 0.05 it indicates that there is a significant effect of work stress variable on turnover intention. The hypothesis is proven and accepted that there is an effect of work value on turnover intention.

2. Work Stress affects Turnover Intention of Generation Z Employee in PT ABC in Java

Based on the T – test result of the work stress variable it has significance value of 0.000 meaning that if the significance value is less than 0.05 it indicates that there is a significant effect of work value variable on turnover intention. The hypothesis is proven and accepted that there is an effect of work stress on turnover intention

3. Work Value and Work Stress affects Turnover Intention of Generation Z Employee in PT ABC in Java

Based on the F – test result of both variables, it has significance value of 0.000 meaning that if the significance value is less than 0.05 it indicates that there are simultaneous effect of both variables on turnover intention. The hypothesis is proven and accepted that both variables simultaneously affecting turnover intention

5) Discussion

1. Work Value affect Turnover Intention of Generation Z Employee in Call Center PT ABC in Java

In the context of turnover intention, work value had been discovered to have an impact on turnover intention, particularly in Generation Z. The social and cohort views are the two ways to look at the work values from a generational cohort. A generation is produced by people who have shared historical experiences in the terms of the social and economic contexts that have changed values, lifestyle, skills and organizational structure (Rafiki &

Hartijasti, 2021). This in line with the theory of social forces. While from the cohort perspective, a generation is a group of people who share the same year of birth and show meaningfully similar views or behaviors that can be seen and assessed (Rafiki & Hartijasti, 2021).

A significance imbalance between an employees work value and the organization's value can cause discontent, decreased in commitment and raise the likelihood in turnover intention (Rafiki & Hartijasti, 2021). Work value itself is defined as an individuals overarching professional objectives and the qualities of a position that are essential to that individual's job satisfaction (Kr & Rajendran, 2019). This research also in accordance with the previous research by Hanaty (2022), found that work values of Generation Z have an impact on the desire to leave the job (Hanaty, 2022).

2. Work Stress affect Turnover Intention of Generation Z Employee in Call Center PT ABC in Java

People experience more pressure to fulfill the increasing requirements in their line of employment. These pressure come from both of individuals personal life and job environment. Individual feels stress as a result of these many expectations. A person's stress level might increase for a variety of reasons, in this research we can see in the table 4.21, the highest reasons of employees feel stressed in the work is because of ambiguity of structures in the organization, proven by the mean value of 4.04 and a significance of 0.011 so that the significance value is less than 0.05, so that there is a significant partial effect of the organization structure dimension variable on turnover intention. This indicating that the main reason employees look for alternative companies to work for is because of unfavorable work circumstances. Employees feel dissatisfied with the lack of information they receive about their roles within the company will feel uncertain about their ability to complete their work, which will result in negative feelings and could convince them to leave their job (Azzahra, Ilmi, & Wijaya, 2021)

Next, is followed by leadership attitude proven by the mean score of 3.76 and the significance of 0.009 so that the significance value is less than 0.05, meaning that there is a partially significant effect of the leadership attitude dimension variable on turnover intention. In every company leaders must take the following actions (Sudiantini & Saputra, 2022):

1. The ability to motivate
Providing motives to work with great diligence in order to achieve company's goals
2. The ability to control emotions
Able to control emotions to avoid dissatisfaction
3. The ability to communicate and listen
Able to effectively communicate and listen to others

If the leader can do the the following abilities above then a numbers of things will be created in the employees such as trust and loyalty and can lower the likelihood of the of the turnover (Widodo, 2023). Otherwise, all the situations above might leave the person feeling mentally and physically spent. The reactions to external demands is stress (Sumrahadi, Azis, Kania, Respati, & Rahmdhanty, 2019). Employees who are under a lot of stress at work may become sick, demotivated, less productive, and less safe. Stress at work also boosts intentions for employee turnover (Zunaidah, Nengyanti, & Hadjri, 2019). The explanations above in relation with the Generation Z is there is a previous research of Sin, Liu, Fong, & Law (2022) found in an interview that work stress is a factor that increasing the intention to turnover.

3. What Causing the Generation Z Employee to leave the workplace and looking for a new one?

This phenomenon is supported by the previous research of Hanaty (2022), found that one of five dimensions that affect turnover intention is social dimension, this related to the theory of Generation Z in many researchs. According to Twenge (2010), social values have to with how individual interacts with co-workers, supervisors and other individuals in the workplace. People who are accustomed to working on group projects and giving presentations are more inclined to place emphasis on the social aspects of the jobs, such as favoring friendly co-workers or an enjoyable workplace. They prefer a stimulating work atmosphere where they can discuss ideas with their colleagues. They enjoy working environments where there is a positive atmosphere, such as good interpersonal and professional relationships with coworkers who have the opportunity to learn and find new stimuli as well as to ask them questions and express doubts. Additionally, they like having good ties with their managers and anticipate frequent feedback and open lines of communication from them (Havlicek, Domeova, & Hlavaty, 2018). Twenge's theory is supported by Agarwal,

Vaghela (2018) found that Generation Z prioritize a social relationship between co – workers, prefer to collaborate and participate together among co – worker in finishing task (Hanaty, 2022)

The organizational structure demonstrates the framework and link between fixed pattern embodiments, varied roles, components or people with varied employment positions, levels of authority and responsibilities. It serves as a tool to help management accomplish its objective. Members of an organization can be significantly impacted by its structure. A previous research shows there is a significant effect with turnover intention related to organizational structure. This indicating that the main reason employees look for alternative companies to work for is because of unfavorable work circumstances. Employees feel dissatisfied with the lack of information they receive about their roles within the company will feel uncertain about their ability to complete their work, which will result in negative feelings and could convince them to leave their job (Azzahra, Ilmi, & Wijaya, 2021). Another reason is a changes of the organizational structure proven have an effect to turnover intention (Subrata & Tamrin, 2018). One of the change in the company's structure is in the form of downsizing, it increased benefits, bonus and site allowances. It also have a significant impact on raising employee's compensation. Downsizing has a significant impact on the turnover intention and resignation, due to it disturbs employee's harmony. Employees feel the need to leave for a safe and secure position as a result of unclear status, demotion and anxiety over waiting his turn to quit next (Subrata & Tamrin, 2018).

Lastly, the leadership attitude dimension shows that Generation Z tends to leave work if their existing leaders do not promote their individuals orientantation (Gaan & Shin, 2022). Another research by Thakur & Dr. Verma, (2020) supports the finding related to leadership style, a good and responsible leadership have a negative effects on the employee's intention to leave the job. They are satisfy with responsible leaders that could increase employees morale (Thakur & Dr. Verma, 2020) and love having a good ties with their managers and anticipate frequent feedback and open lines of communication from them (Havlicek, Domeova, & Hlavaty, 2018), it will leads to low turnover intention in the job (Thakur & Dr. Verma, 2020). The theory of social exchange could be explain to this phenomenon. According to the theory, leaders and employee exchange resources through a series of interaction procedures that could involve material or intangible goods, leading to the creation of responsibilities (Gaan & Shin, 2022). According to the social exchange theory, the employee's perception of the leader's capacity for mutually beneficial personal and professional interaction can predict withdrawal behavior or intention to leave the work (Gaan & Shin, 2022).

Business Solution

Based on this research analysis, using indicators and dimensions on the influential variables, it is discovered that social dimensions, unclear structures and leadership style are the factors that have the most effect on turnover intention. The author propose programs and initiatives based on the results mentioned above that aim to lessen the impact of variables on turnover intention such as team building, intergroup interaction, role clarity and lastly, leadership development.

1) High Involvement Organizational

Creating a digital program called ABCheers. ABCheers is a platform designed and facilitated for the employees encouraged by the company to communicate and share their opinions related to the work. Using this method helps to foster a collaboration, communication and innovation for the employees

2) Team Building and Intergroup

The proposed team building is personality – based team building and activity based team building. Personality based team building is chosen in order to enhance communication skills amongst employees and expects them to respect and understand one another, also it's selected to improve group cohesion and efficiency. There are various games that can be selected to test the personality between employees such as MBTI and the games are made by combined personality differences between employees.

While the selected program for intergroup interaction is activity based team building. The activity require participants to solve problems, take on variety of roles and face challenges. It is chosen in order to foster harmony, interaction between groups while getting to know each employee better.

3) Role Clarity

Role clarity is defined as the level of understanding an employee is related to the extent of his role expected by the company in carrying out his work (Khusnah & Anugraini, 2022). The role clarity is in form of :

1. Give a corporate orientation to all employees and make sure they understand their responsibilities within their immediate work team or unit, program area and organization as a whole
2. Create an updated role and position description
3. Assists and ensure employees to work according to their roles
4. Encourage employees to consult to their manager regarding to the ambiguity of their roles.

4) Leadership Development

It is a program in the form of training design for prospective leaders to have the characteristics and abilities of a leader. The priority is on gaining the abilities and expertise that the organization believes it will be required to carry out future plans and manage the company. The skills and knowledge of a group of organization members are also changed in order to increase their effectiveness or develop the capabilities of an organizational system. The application for this program includes :

1. Assessment

The assesment identifies the skills that are thought to distinguish effective leaders in the organization. It entails comprehending the experiences and information. The corporate strategy will need to be carried out by future leaders. It contains actions, decisions and tasks that participants expected to accomplish more effectively resulting from training.

2. Design the Training

This part is to determines the development intervention's goals. It is expected to outline both the outcomes anticipated of a capable leader and the methods used to accomplish those outcomes. The methodologies should be selected from a wide range varieties of programs such as coaching, simulation, case studies and on the job training.

3. Deliver the Training

It is the stage to implements the designed program for the leadership development.

4. Evaluate the training

The final step evaluates the program to see if it achieved the goals, if it was helpful for the candidates, assess if they learned and improved and the new abilities obtained from the program process were put to use in their regular job activities.

CONCLUSIONS

This study found that there is an impact of work stress and work values on turnover intention, with the social dimension of work stress and the dimensions of organizational structure and leadership attitude having the most influence on Generation Z employees at PT ABC in Java. there are business solutions offered to help reduce the effect of the dimension that causing turnover intention such as creating a sharing and discussion platform for employees, team building, role clarity and leadership development. The author suggests for future researchers to analyze using other variables for Generation Z to broaden the research on the generation.

REFERENCES

1. Arshad, M. Z., Shahidan, A. N., Siam, I. M., & Alshuaibi, A. S. (2020). Effect of Role Conflict and Work Overload on Job Stress: A Case of Banking Sector Employees. *Talent Development & Excellence Vol.12, No.3s*, 2686 - 2696.
2. Azzahra, S., Ilmi, Z., & Wijaya, A. (2021). The Influence of Role Ambiguity, Job Stress and Leadership on Job Satisfaction and Employee Turnover at PT. Bank BRI Syariah Samarinda. *Saudi J Bus Manag Stud*, 6(1), 15-23.
3. Dhanpat, N. M. (2018). Exploring employee retention and intention to leave within a call centre. *South African Journal of Human Resource Management* 16(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajhrm.v16i0.905>.
4. Doellgastt, V., & O'Brady, S. (2020). *Making call center jobs better: The relationship between management practices and worker stress*. ILR School, Cornell University and DeGroote School of Business, McMaster University.
5. Dziuba, S. T., Ingaldi, M., & Zhuravskaya, M. (2020). EMPLOYEES JOB SATISFACTION AND THEIR WORK PERFORMANCE AS ELEMENTS INFLUENCING WORK SAFETY. *CzOTO 2020, volume 2, issue 1, pp. 18-25, 18-25*.

6. Francis, T., & Hoefel, F. (2018, November). *True Gen': Generation Z and its implications for companies*. Retrieved from McKinsey&Company: <https://www.mckinsey.com/~media/McKinsey/Industries/Consumer%20Packaged%20Goods/Our%20Insights/True%20Gen%20Generation%20Z%20and%20its%20implications%20for%20companies/Generation-Z-and-its-implication-for-companies.pdf>
7. Gaan, N., & Shin, Y. (2022). Generation Z software employees turnover intention. *Curr Psychol*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-03847-9>.
8. Hanaty, C. (2022). The Impact of Workplace Values on Turnover Intention of Generation Z: The Case of Government Employees in Rabat. *Revue des Sciences Humaines et Sociales de l'Académie du Royaume du Maroc • Vol. I • N°1 •*, 63-80.
9. Havlicek, J., Domeova, L., & Hlavaty, R. (2018). GEN Z IN THE WORKPLACE: EXPECTATIONS, COMMUNICATION AND RELATIONSHIPS. *ERIE*, 76-82.
10. Khusnah, H., & Anugraini, M. (2022). PENGUKURAN KINERJA NON KEUANGAN TERHADAP KINERJA KARYAWAN: EFEK MEDIASI DARI ROLE CLARITY DAN KOMITMEN ORGANISASI. *Jurnal Media Mahardhika VOL 20 No. 2*, 287-293.
11. Kr, S., & Rajendran, V. (2019). Work Values of Gen Z. *DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22500.19845*.
12. Kr, S., & Rajendran, V. (2019). Work Values of Gen-Z. *KCT Business School*, DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22500.19845.
13. Maulana, M. H. (2022). DARI PERSEPSI ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE HINGGA PENGARUH JOB SATISFACTION DAN JOB STRESS TERHADAP TURNOVER INTENTION PADA KARYAWAN GENERASI MILENIAL DAN GENERASI Z. *Journal of Advances in Digital Business and Entrepreneurship - VOL. 01 NO. 01 SEPTEMBER*, 1-5.
14. Mobley, W. H. (2011). *Pergantian Karyawan: Sebab, Akibat dan Pengendaliannya (Terjemahan)*. Jakarta: PT Pustaka Binaman Pressindo.
15. Nanda, A. (2019). The Effect of Psychological Work Environment and Work Loads on Turnover Interest, Work Stress as an Intervening Variable. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, volume 120, 225-231.
16. Posey, C. N. (2019). Job-shock influence on call-center turnover. *Performance Improvement*,58(5), 22–32. <http://doi.org/10.1002/pfi.21866>.
17. Racolta-Paina, N. D., & Irini, R. D. (2021). Generation Z in the Workplace through the Lenses of Human Resource Professionals – A Qualitative Study. *Quality Access to Success Vol. 22, No. 18 3*, 78-85.
18. Rafiki, M., & Hartijasti, Y. (2021). Generational Differences in Dimensions of Work Values of Indonesian Permanent Employees. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, volume 647, 298-303.
19. Santoso, A. L., Sitompul, S. A., & Budiartanto, A. (2018). Burnout, Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intention. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research (JBRMR)*, Vol. 13 Issue 1, 62-69.
20. Sharma, R., Ms. Sharma, R., & Agarwal, P. K. (June 2021). EFFECT OF STRESS AT WORKPLACE AND ITS MANAGEMENT. *VSRD International Journal of Business and Management Research*, Vol. XI Issue I, 1-12.
21. Stobiecka, J., & Kania, S. P. (2022). MANAGING STRESS AS A KEY ELEMENT OF THE COMPETITION IN THE WORKPLACE BASED ON THE EXAMPLE OF GENERATIONS Y AND Z. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357991886>.
22. Subrata, G., & Tamrin, M. (2018). PENGARUH PERUBAHAN STRUKTUR ORGANISASI TERHADAP TINGGINYA TURN OVER INTENTION. *AKADEMIKA; Vol. 16. No.1 Februari* , 38-49.
23. Sudiantini, D., & Saputra, F. (2022). The Influence of Leadership Style: Job Satisfaction, Employee Loyalty and Commitment at PT Lensa Potret Mandiri. *Formosa Journal of sustainable Research (FJSR)*, 1(3), , 467-478.
24. Sulistiobudi, R. A., & Hutabarat, H. N. (2022). Adaptation of Work Values Instrument in Indonesian Final Year University Students. *Front. Psychol.* 13:858688., 1-9.
25. Sumrahadi, Azis, E., Kania, I., Respati, N. P., & Rahmdhanty, A. (2019). Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional, Stres Kerja, Kepuasan Kerja, dan Turnover Intention pada Karyawan Perusahaan Penyedia Jasa Konsultasi Pengembangan Sumberdaya Manusia. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial, Politik & Humaniora. Vol.1 No.1*, 1-16.

26. Thakur, D. J., & Dr. Verma, P. (2020). THE IMPACT OF LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEE'S TURNOVER INTENTION. *PJAE*, 17 (6) , 1693-1704.
27. Widodo, D. S. (2023). The Effect of Leadership Style on Turnover Intention and Job Satisfaction. *International Journal of Psychology and Health Science Vol. 1, No. 1 January*, 19-29.
28. Xueting, X. (2022). Research, Critical Review of Quantitative and Qualitative. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research, volume 670*, 956-959.
29. Zito, M., Emanuel, F., Molino, M., Cortese, C. G., Ghislieri, C., & Colombo, L. (2018). Turnover intentions in a call center: The role of emotional dissonance, job resources, and job satisfaction. *PLoS ONE 13 (2): e0192126*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.>, 1-16.
30. Zunaidah, Nengyanti, & Hadjri, M. I. (2019). Work Stress, Job Satisfaction, And Turnover Intention: Case Study On Regional Development Banks In Southern Sumatera. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH VOLUME 8, ISSUE 07, JULY*, 583-586.

Cite this Article: Darian Kashfitanto, Hary Febriansyah (2023). The Effect of Work Stress and Work Values on Turnover Intention of Generation Z Employees in Call Center Company (Case Study of PT ABC in Java, Indonesia). International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(7), 3962-3974